

S. No.	Paper Title	Page No.
1.	Study on Strengthening of Concrete by using Environmental Degraded Materials	4
2.	Study the Cracks and Behaviour of Admixture in Cracked Concrete Structure: A review paper	9
3.	Study on Silica Fume Concrete	15
4.	Feasibility Analysis of RC Lean Structural Wall Building Subjected to Seismic Loading	17
5.	Study on Partial Replacement of Sand with Glass Waste in Concrete	26
6.	A Review on Environmental Flow Estimation: Methods and Methodologies	29
7.	Utilization of red mud as a partial replacement of binder content in concrete	37
8.	Enhancing the Acceptance of Roof Top Rain Water Harvesting by increasing the usability of Collected Water and Cost Optimization	42
9.	Short term strategies for maintaining CPCB norms of Stack emission at Steel Industry in India. A perspective of Sinter Plant 2 - Bhilai Steel Plant.	48
10.	Green Roof – A Sustainable Solution for Built Environment	61
11.	A Review on Upscaling of Fluid Flow through Heterogeneous Porous Media	67
12.	Assessment of pollution potential of urban lakes using NSFQI and CCMEWQI Water Quality Indices	77
13.	An Approach on Assessing Sustainability of Ground Improvement by Multi Criteria Assessment	85
14.	Study of repair works for overhead RCC water storage tank	92
15.	Study of Environment Impact Assessment on Highway Project	95
16.	A Review: Study on the behavior of Bolted Steel Angles under Tension	104
17.	Comparative Study of Parallel Flange Section and Tapered Flange Section	115
18.	Investigation of Optimum Speed on Highway	120
19.	Evaluating the properties of self healing bacterial concrete dosed with bacillus subtilis	123
20.	Reuse of Plastic waste in paver blocks	133

S. No.	Paper Title	Page No.
21.	Demolished Concrete Aggregates – An Effective Alternate To Future Of Construction For Low Cost Housing.	138
22.	Study of Industrial shed with Conventional Roofing System & Innovative Self Supporting Roofing System: A review paper	146
23.	Sedimentation Appraisal in between Bhaijhar Barrage and Turkadih Bridge along Arpa River in Bilaspur (CG)	153
24.	Use of Waste Foundry Sand in Evolution of Low Cost Concrete: A Review Paper	161
25.	Design Aid to IS 800-2007: Safe Load for Angle Struts	169
26.	Study on Utilization of Waste Plastic as Fibres in Fibre Reinforced Concrete	189
27.	Comparative Study of Analysis Design of Water Tank as Per Indian Standards and Computer Codes	194
28.	E -Waste Management in India: Issues and challenges	197
29.	Data Assimilation for Imputing Missing Values in In-situ Soil Moisture Observations	203
30.	Study of Behaviour of Multi-Storey Building with Shear Walls: A Review Paper	215
31.	Study on Development of Fly Ash – Red Mud based Geopolymer Concrete Paver Block	222
32.	Study of Wind Load on Building Frame on Sloping Ground Surface	234
33.	A Review on Testing, Design, and Remediation of Soil Engineering	237
34.	Dynamic Analysis of Steel Buildings with Lead Rubber Base Isolator	252
35.	Water Requirement Assessment of Tandula Reservoir Command Area	257
36.	Study of Ambient Air and Noise quality in Bhalai during Diwali festival	265
37.	Semi-distributed Storm Water Management Model for Urban Flood Mitigation and Management through LID's	269
38.	An appraisal to identify the Impact of Urban Heat Island effect using Remote Sensing Data	275
39.	Experimental Studies of Concrete by Partially Replacement of Cement & Fine Aggregate Using Glass Powder and Granite Dust	283

S. No.	Paper Title	Page No.
40.	Experimental Studies of Concrete by Partially Replacement of Cement & Sand Using Marble Dust	289
41.	Comparative Study on Retrofitting Methods	294
42.	Durability Design of Concrete Structures in Tropics: The Meteorological Aspects	300
43.	Design of Rain Water Harvesting – A Campus Case Study	307
44.	The Effect of Corrosion Damage on Low Cycle Fatigue of Steel Bar	315
45.	A Short Review of Experimental Approaches for the Estimation of Drying Diffusivity of Porous Building Materials	320

Semi-distributed Storm Water Management Model for Urban Flood Mitigation and Management through LID's

Manish Kumar Sinha^{1, 2}, Monika Sharma^{1*}, Sushmita Gouraha¹

¹Department of Environmental and Water resources engineering, UTD, CSVTU Bhilai, India.

²Department of Engineering Geology and Hydrogeology, RWTH Aachen University, Germany.

Email: sinha@lih.rwth-aachen.de

*Monika Sharma, Email: monikasharma3096@gmail.com

Abstract

The management of the chronic urban flooding is one of the leading challenges presently facing in any parts of the India. Impact of flood rates can be observed in high rates due to increasing in impervious area, climate change and a lack of review when adopting drainage network. A SWMM (storm water management model) is an effective tool to analysis the amount to which the proposed solution will mitigate the flooding in the study area. The pilot study area taken in this study is highly influenced by impact of storm water generation due to increase in buildup areas in the city. The present study reveals the effectiveness and modality of SWMM for best LID (Low Impact Development) controls for real world solutions.

Keywords: Flood management, Drainage network, Low Impact Development, SWMM.

Introduction:

Urban flooding is a rising phenomenon in recent time. It is specific in the fact that the cause is a lack of drainage in an urban area. Problem associated with urban floods increases if no changes are made to unplanned expansion and poor management of urban area introduce land degradation, water logging, deterioration of roads an increase of impervious land increases the impermeability of land due to urbanization. Flooding give rise to hydrological problems which cause degradation of the quality of flows in both the drainage networks serving the urban area and the underlying aquifers.

An urban flood occurs when water overflow drainage, water logging (zammer et al 2013). In recent scenario, climatic change main factor is, the intensity of rainfall is more in short duration due to which flooding in urban areas is very common (Awakimjan et al 2015). The flooding is natural phenomenon but human activities has significantly increase the flood risk (Gupta and Nair 2011; Prasad 2014) over the last few era, the priority of developing cities is different according to their growth.

The main aim of urban drainage is drainage hygiene, environmental protection, flood protection (choc at et al, 2007) for larger and stronger storms, extensive land use changes & increasing climatic variability is to be treat with appropriate water management method (XU el at 2015), urban flood as a risk, characterized by (Thieken et al, 2006) the exceedance chances of the conceivably harming flood situation in a given area with determined time frame.

Flood inundation modelling has major role in flood mitigation and minimizing its effects. Most flooding is brought about by substantial and intense precipitation in zones where lacking of drainage network framework can't manage abundance measure of runoff effectively. Lack of poor storm water management practices in urban area can be even more dangerous than many natural disasters.

Futuristic Trends in Science, Technology and Management for National Development

A low impact development (LID) urban drainage uses efficient and tempting micro scale techniques to control unplanned structure of watershed, minimize pollution and most important to control storm water runoff. LID is a generally new idea in storm water the executives, which uses a site structure system with an objective of keeping up or recreating the pre improvement hydrologic routine utilizing plan procedures to make a practically equal hydrologic scene (U.S EPA,2000).LID is a generally new idea in storm water the executives, which uses a site structure system with an objective of keeping up or recreating the pre improvement hydrologic routine utilizing plan procedures to make a practically equal hydrologic scene (U. S EPA,2000). LID also have the advantage of effectively removing nutrients, reducing the volume and intensity of storm water flows because of the deficiencies related to urbanization, problem of drainage as discussed above, there is an acute need to devise an innovative LID planning tool for engineers and decision makers.

Materials and Methods:

Study Area:

Raipur city is the capital of Chhattisgarh; it is formerly a part of Madhya Pradesh before Chhattisgarh was formed on Nov 2000.The city is administrated by Raipur municipal cooperation (RMC). Raipur district is located in the center of the Chhattisgarh state and is bounded by East longitude 81.586° and 81.683° and by north latitude 21.201° and 21.324°.Rainfall is endowed with high rainfall. The district receives its rainfall mainly from the south-west monsoon. Raipur has witnessed a high growth rate in population, which has not been matched with a corresponding sanitation infrastructure (RMC et. al.2011).

Figure 1: Location map of the study area

Futuristic Trends in Science, Technology and Management for National Development

The consequence- ‘sanitation problem’. Despite being a historically and archaeologically important city with several beautiful lakes. Raipur is categorized under ‘critically polluted area’ by central pollution control board. Reason behind is the lack of sanitation infrastructure to meet the demands of the growing population, lack of appropriate operation and maintenance (city sanitation plan for Raipur) with poor drainage network, inadequate covering the drains, dumping of solid waste, especially low lying areas for almost a period of month, with 23 flood prone areas identified in city limits (city sanitation plan for Raipur).

Urban overflow amount and quality establish issues of both chronic and current nature. Urban communities, since long, have accepted the accountability of control of storm water flooding and treatment of point source (e.g. Metropolitan sewage) of waste water.

The EPA storm water management model (SWMM), first created in 1969. It was one of the main such models. It has been continually maintained & updated and is may be the best known and most generally utilized of the accessible urban runoff quantity/quality models (Huber and roesner,2013). SWMM is a dynamic rainfall runoff simulation model used for single event or long term (continuous) simulation of runoff quantity and quality from primarily urban areas. SWMM tracks the quantity & quality of runoff generated within each pipe and channel during a simulation period comprise of multiple time steps.

The hydraulic procedures happening with in SWMM conveyance compartment include:

Figure 2: EPA-SWMM flood simulation and management process (Used after USEPA 2000)

Futuristic Trends in Science, Technology and Management for National Development

- Outside inflow of surface runoff, ground water interflow, precipitation subordinate, rainfall-dependent infiltration/inflow.
- Pipes and storage units, unsteady, on uniform flow routing through any configuration of open channels, pipes and storage units.
- Different conceivable stream routines, for ex backwater, surcharging, switch stream.

Data Required:

SWMM’S visual objects may be arranged together to represent a storm water drainage network framework. These items can be shown on a guide in the SWMM work space.

1. Rain gauge
2. Sub catchment
3. Junction nodes
4. Conduits

Rainfall Analysis:

To run the model in SWMM, it is necessary to feed the rainfall time series data in hourly format. Generation of IDF (intensity duration frequency curve) for design period of rainfall of past and generate for future scenario and simulate in SWMM to know the possibility of flood in that storm.

Sustainable Approach:

In 1972, US Federal Clean Water Act has fundamentally extended storm water management in the United States from flood mitigation into both storm water quality and quantity controls. So one of them is dispose on site runoff volume using device.

Low impact development (LID) is an ecologically – based storm water management approach favoring soft engineering to manage rainfall on site through vegetated treatment network. The goal of lid is to sustain a site predevelopment hydrologic regime by using technique that infiltrate, filter store and evaporate storm water close to it source.

Figure 3: EPA-SWMM semi-distributed flood simulation protocol

Source: Storm water management user manual

Common LID'S: in-built

1. Bio-retention/rain gardens
2. Disconnection of impervious areas
3. Dry wells
4. Filter strips
5. Grassed swales/bio-retention swales
6. Infiltration trenches
7. Permeable pavement
8. Rain barrels
9. Vegetated roofs

Figure 4: Examples of low impact development (LID) practices

Summary and Conclusion:

This paper present about urban flooding due to unplanned expansion and with different factors like intensity of storm at that duration in urban area. Urban development is causing significant environmental impact, ecosystem, losing vegetative area and more flooding, higher level of contaminants in receiving water. Paper also describes a feasible application of EPA SWMM. The parameters encoded into the model were controlled by various method and a few strategies were utilized for their assurance so as to survey their effect, moreover observed discharge and precipitation information, essential to adjust the model, were resolved either for old or current storm events. It gives a framework which comprehends the hydrological forms that occur in urban domain and shows that a variety of indirect data can be useful for a watershed model application.

It is concluded that there is need to provide a sustainable approach in the form of LID (Low impact development) for storm water management system and practices to reduce the flooding and to improve the water availability and the ground water recharge in urban areas.

References:

- [1] GIZ (2008) "City Sanitation Plan for Raipur
- [2] Gupta, A.K. and Nair, S.S., 2011. Urban floods in Bangalore and Chennai: risk management challenges and lessons for sustainable urban ecology. *Current Science (Bangalore)*, 100(11), pp.1638-1645.
- [3] Huber, W. and Roesner, L., 2012. The History and Evolution of the EPA SWMM.
- [4] Khan, A.A. and Ahmad, M., 2014. Integration of Storm water Drains with Lakes: Expectations and Reality-A Case of Raipur, India. *Hydrology: Current Research*, 5(2), p.1.
- [5] Liu, J., Guo, L.H., Zhang, J.T. and Lv, T., 2006. Study on simulation of drainage and flooding in urban areas of shanghai based on improved SWMM. *China water & wastewater*, 22(21), pp.64-66.
- [6] Pathak, H. and Chaudhari, P., 2015. Simulation of best management practices using SWMM. *Int. Res. J. Eng. Technol.*, 2(1), pp.129-132.
- [7] Raipur, Wikipedia, the free Encyclopedia.
- [8] Rangari, V.A., Gonugunta, R., Umamahesh, N.V., Patel, A.K. and Bhatt, C.M., 2018. 1D-2D Modeling Of Urban Floods and Risk Map Generation for the Part of Hyderabad City. *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing & Spatial Information Sciences*.
- [9] Rangari, V.A., Sridhar, V., Umamahesh, N.V. and Patel, A.K., Rainfall runoff modeling of urban area using HEC-HMS: A case study of Hyderabad city.
- [10] Thielen, A., Merz, B., Kreibich, H. and Apel, H., 2006, September. Methods for flood risk assessment: Concepts and challenges. In *International workshop on flash floods in urban areas* (pp. 1-12).
- [11] US Environmental Protection Agency, 2000. Low impact development (LID): A literature review. Office of Water EPA-841-B-00-005.

